

Mapping optimal locations of forest biomass for solar-powered biorefinery plants in the Mediterranean region

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ABSTRACT

This study assesses forest aboveground biomass (AGB), solar irradiation, and road connectivity to determine the optimal number and distribution of solar-powered biorefinery (SPB) plants in three Mediterranean countries. AGB availability was evaluated by applying spatial restrictions (forest cover, elevation, slope, and soil type) and combined them into a multi-criteria analysis (MCA). Subsequently, two of these factors, canopy cover and slope, along with three additional ones, effective AGB, vegetation productivity, and road proximity, were weighted to determine a suitability score, normalised from [0-1] and aggregated to 1 km resolution. Suitability maps were integrated into a decision support system to cluster suitable areas and identify optimal host cities. High suitability pixels (values > 0.5) were assigned to nearby (<100 km) and large cities (>250,000 inhabitants). A final index, weighted inversely by distance, was then calculated to assign a total suitability score to each city. A balance between selecting too few cities, which limits AGB availability due to transportation costs, and selecting too many cities, which adds no marginal AGB relative to the estimated costs of building a SPB plant, was found applying a simulated annealing method to a cost-function. A spatial database was developed for Spain, Italy and Greece that includes: (i) raster suitability maps in a geographic coordinate system at ~1 ha pixel resolution, (ii) raster suitability maps in a cartographic coordinate system at 1 km resolution, and (iii) a vector dataset of high suitability points with the five attributes used in the MCA.

1. Introduction

To strengthen the circular economy, the European Commission has implemented a Bioeconomy Strategy promoting biomass production and its conversion into food, materials, and bioenergy products. Bioenergy is essential for reaching the EU's climate and energy targets for 2030 [1] and climate neutrality by 2050 [2], developing a circular economy with a key role in carbon neutrality [3]. Lignocellulosic biomass, particularly forest aboveground biomass (AGB), is one of the major renewable energy sources and can serve as a feedstock for bioenergy and bioproducts. Through thermochemical processes, it can be converted into solid, liquid, or gaseous biofuels and high-value chemicals [4], as well as heat, electricity, and transportation fuels [5]. This pathway reduces dependence on fossil fuel, which is associated with environmental degradation, greenhouse gas emissions, and often imported resources [6]. For example, residential heating in EU countries was predominantly fossil fuel-based in 2015 (70%), with 69% imported [7]. By 2020, the EU-27 obtained 22% of its total energy consumption from renewable sources, with a target of 32% set for 2050. Notably, around 60% of this

renewable energy was derived from AGB [8]. To further accelerate this transition, the European Commission has launched the Renewable Energy Power EU plan [9].

Bioenergy can be produced in various forms, including solid biofuels (firewood, pellets, briquettes, wood chips, and charcoal), as well as liquid biofuels and biogas derived from AGB through biochemical and thermochemical processes. In thermochemical conversion, the main pathways are direct combustion, gasification, and pyrolysis [10], producing bio-oil, biochar, and syngas [11]. Among these methods, pyrolysis is relatively fast and requires less biomass pretreatment than enzymatic conversion [12]. However, thermochemical processes require substantial energy inputs to convert AGB into biofuels. To address this challenge, integrating alternative renewable energy sources can improve long-term sustainability of bioenergy and bioproducts production. In particular, solar power, with high irradiation in many regions, can supply renewable heat for biomass conversion [13], supporting biofuel production and contributing to green energy generation [14].

Promoting bioenergy and bioproduct production requires placing

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SPB plants near forest AGB sources to optimise transport, minimise CO₂ emissions, and convert biomass into high-energy-value products, which can create new value chains through the pyrolysis process. Quantifying AGB availability is therefore essential for assessing its bioproduct potential. Nevertheless, a robust evaluation of areas capable of sustainably supplying forest AGB must also consider ecological and operational factors, including biodiversity conservation, forest degradation, mechanisation constraints, topography, and road accessibility. Forest productivity, commonly represented by net primary production (NPP), which reflects biomass accumulation, is particularly relevant for identifying regions capable of supplying a consistent and sustainable flow of forest AGB for long-term pyrolysis-based production. In Europe, many countries rely on sample-based National Forest Inventories, commonly conducted every 5-10 years, to generate reliable AGB and forest growth statistics [15], supporting the identification of suitable areas for establishing SPBs. Additional constraints include topography and road accessibility. Potentially viable areas may be located on steep terrains or

fragile soils, where timber extraction is environmentally risky, time-consuming, and quite expensive [16]. In such cases, complex harvesting systems, such as cable yarding operations on steep slopes, may be required [17]. Additionally, areas with a low road density can indirectly reduce productivity and significantly increase costs during wood extraction and transportation to the SPBs [18]. Therefore, further research is required to identify optimal SPB locations by jointly considering forest AGB suitability and solar energy availability. Previous studies have optimised biorefinery siting based on bio-resources and environment criteria [19], or focused on agricultural biomass [20]. However, comprehensive assessments integrating forest AGB constraints with solar energy requirements remain scarce in the Mediterranean region.

The main aim of this study was to identify suitable areas for establishing SPBs in southern Europe (Spain, Italy, and Greece) by integrating multiple spatial variables into a multi-criteria analysis (MCA). These variables included forest AGB availability, productivity, vegetation

Fig. 1. Selected countries in southern Europe (top) and the forest AGB (Mg/ha) available for the year 2020 along with the annual DNI (kWh/m²) distribution (bottom).

characteristics, terrain features, and road networks. The study also aimed to pinpoint regions combining high solar irradiation, strong road infrastructure, and proximity to areas with high AGB suitability index (SI). To achieve this, four objectives were defined: i) to identify key variables that drive the primary restrictions for establishing suitable areas for SPBs and to determine the effective forest AGB available, ii) to normalize these variables using utility functions and assign weights through various MCA scenarios to derive SIs, iii) to identify optimal areas through clustering and evaluate scenarios via sensitivity analysis; and iv) to determine regions within each cluster with high solar irradiation and adequate infrastructure for storing and treating the forest AGB, including a tree species classification oriented toward pine and oak species.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study area

The study area included: Spain, Italy, and Greece (Fig. 1). In Spain, the Canary and Balearic Islands were excluded due to their geographic constraints, while the cities of Ceuta and Melilla were also omitted because of their limited surface area. Similarly, several small Italian and Greek islands were excluded because of logistical difficulties in transporting forest AGB. Fig. 1 illustrates two key variables for identifying optimal SPB locations: forest AGB [21] and direct normal irradiation (DNI) [22]. All three countries demonstrate considerable potential for forest AGB availability. However, regions with the highest biomass stocks, such as northern Spain and the alpine zones of northern Italy, generally coincide with lower DNI values. This pattern is expected, as high vegetation productivity is associated with a high-water regime. Consequently, areas with high DNI are typically found in extremely dry vegetation conditions, where AGB availability is limited. Nevertheless, some regions achieve a balance between sufficient AGB availability and the minimum DNI required to support thermochemical processes using concentrated solar power.

2.2. Raster inputs used to determine effective AGB availability

The raster datasets used to assess AGB for SPB pyrolysis plants were obtained from multiple European and global sources and masked to Spain, Italy, and Greece (Fig. 2). All datasets were standardised to the WGS84 coordinate system (EPSG:4326) with an approximate pixel

resolution of 1 ha. Total AGB from all land uses was initially considered [21] and then filtered using the CORINE Land Cover map 2018 [23] to isolate forest-related AGB. From the 44 land-use classes, eight were retained: broadleaved, coniferous, and mixed forests, along with natural grasslands, moors and heathlands, sclerophyllous vegetation, transitional woodland-shrub, and agroforestry areas.

Topographic characteristics were derived from ALOS World 3D data [24]. A slope threshold of 50% was applied, reflecting the operational challenges and high costs of extracting AGB on steep terrain. According to [25], ground-based harvesting machines are recommended for slopes up to 30%. Slopes between 31% and 60% are considered critical, while those exceeding 60% are classified as very critical, where such machinery becomes impractical. In these cases, cable logging remains the only viable option; however, it is an extremely costly method for supplying SPB plants. Therefore, adopting a 50% slope threshold strikes a balance by including additional terrain while maintaining manageable operational risks, as mentioned by [26] in some examples. In addition, AGB is limited at high altitudes. In the Spanish Pyrenees and Italian Alps, vegetation above 2300 and 2500 m a.s.l. is sparse [27] and subject to harsh conditions, including snow and ice. Accordingly, an elevation threshold of 2500 m a.s.l. was applied.

Soil properties were classified according to the World Reference Base, including 32 soil groups [28]. Five groups, such as *Cryosols*, *Gleysols*, *Histosols*, *Leptosols*, and *Planosols* were excluded due to their fragility for forest mechanisation and conservation importance. Soil data were obtained from SoilGrids, with raster layers downloaded for Spain, Italy, and Greece and adjusted to the respective geographic extents of each country. The original resolution of the dataset was 250 m [29]. Forest cover was also considered a restriction. Although no international regulations define a minimum forest cover for harvesting operations, low coverage areas are generally avoided to prevent degradation and deforestation. Forest cover fractions were updated using forest gain and loss datasets [30], acknowledging that forest AGB is dynamic and influenced by disturbances and seasonal or interannual variability. Following [31], lower forest cover is associated with reduced harvesting intensity; therefore, only pixels with >50% forest cover were retained, which also correlates with higher AGB availability and productivity. Protected areas, specifically those within the Natura 2000 network [32], present another limitation. Covering 788,000 km² (18% of EU land) and allowing certain human activities under diverse management regimes [33], Natura 2000 areas were not directly excluded. Instead, they were treated as conditional: a pixel otherwise suitable for SPB establishment

Fig. 2. Workflow from total AGB filtered by CORINE land cover (2018), retaining only forest-related land uses. Five restrictions were applied to obtain effective AGB. Subsequently, a MCA was performed, normalising variables to a [0-1] scale. The highest SI, based on five criteria primarily related to vegetation and accessibility, identified the optimal locations for establishing SPB pyrolysis plants.

that overlap with Natura 2000 areas were flagged for further local assessment, distinguishing unrestricted areas from those requiring additional regulatory consideration.

2.3. Raster inputs for MCA

Effective AGB areas resulted from applying restrictions to the total AGB. Five variables were then considered in a MCA to later define a SI (Fig. 2), ranging from [0-1], prioritising areas with high AGB accompanied with well-developed road infrastructure to supply SPB plants. Vegetation characteristics included effective AGB, NPP [34], and canopy cover [30]. Yet, AGB availability is not enough to characterise suitable areas, as forest growth must also be considered. To address this, NPP, which is a raster layer at 300 m spatial resolution, reports biomass increments through carbon sequestration from 2023 to the present. Updated forest cover data [30] was included to capture changes from forest disturbances to prevent degradation in low coverage areas. On the other hand, accessibility was assessed using slope and road network density. Slope data followed the threshold applied for effective AGB [24]. Road proximity was initially derived from a global highway dataset [35] but was replaced with OpenStreetMap (OSM) data to include all road types, providing a more comprehensive and up-to-date raster. Although additional variables could refine the MCA, including too many factors may reduce robustness and increase uncertainty.

2.4. Normalisation functions

All MCA variables were normalised to [0,1] using a ramp function $R(x)$ (Formula 1), with the 1st and 99th percentiles as thresholds to reduce outlier influence. Alternative ranges (2nd-98th and 5th-95th) are shown in Figures A1-A3. Positive ramps were applied to AGB, productivity, and forest cover, while slope and road proximity employed a negative ramp, as these variables have respectively a positive and negative correlation with the definition of the SI. This approach preserves meaningful variation, allowing comparison across variables with different units, and ensures balance integration into the MCA, particularly for variables with broad ranges such as AGB or road proximity.

$$R(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \leq x_{min} \\ \frac{x - x_{min}}{x_{max} - x_{min}} & \text{if } x_{min} < x < x_{max} \\ 1 & \text{if } x \geq x_{max} \end{cases} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

In Formula 1, x_{min} and x_{max} define the ramp bounds, determined from each variable's histogram (Figures A1-A3). Table A1 summarises all variables and their frequency distributions, supporting the choice of thresholds. The normalisation provided final maps with ranges between [0-1] for all five variables.

2.5. Multi-criteria scenarios and sensitivity analysis

Eight scenarios were defined by calculating the optimal combination of variables based on their sensitivity to SI values (Table 1). Pairwise comparisons assessed each variable's effect while keeping others constant, revealing how changes influenced final SI (Fig. 3).

Slope was the least sensitive variable, exhibiting a near-zero effect on SI (Fig. 3), and its weight was fixed at 0.05 in all scenarios. In contrast, AGB availability was the most influential factor. Forest cover and road proximity also exhibited substantial weight variability (0.1 to 0.4), reflecting their pivotal role in assessing AGB suitability, while NPP displayed lower sensitivity (0.05 to 0.20) to balance its influence (Figure A4). Table 1 summarises the calibrated weights for all eight scenarios, with maximum values (0.40) highlighted in bold.

2.6. Aggregating pixels

Suitability maps at 100 m resolution, derived from different weight combinations, were aggregated to a 1 km grid using the Lambert Azimuthal Equal Area projection (EPSG:3035), centred at 10°E, 52°N. This ensures alignment with EU-wide geospatial guidelines under the INSPIRE Directive (2007/2/EC). Aggregation used a weighted sum with a uniform square kernel, where each 1 km pixel incorporates 100 of initial 100 m pixels. Resulting values, normalised to [0-1], representing the total expected suitability into 1 km² (Fig. 4).

2.7. Optimal allocation of potential SPB pyrolysis plants

After aggregating data to 1 km pixels, optimal SPB plant locations were determined by iteratively assessing different numbers and locations of plants. The AGB suitability map was clustered into K groups, with candidate locations restricted to large cities (>250,000 inhabitants) to ensure well-developed road networks. Each city was assumed to collect all AGB within its assigned cluster, with each pixel assigned to only one city (Fig. 5). City scores were calculated as the weighted sum of SI values for all assigned pixels, considering only high SI pixels within 100 km, inversely weighted by the distance to the

Table 1

Eight scenarios were defined by assigning different weights to the five variables, informed by a two-variable sensitivity analysis using the interquartile range (10th to 90th percentile).

Scenario	AGB availability	NPP	Forest cover	Slope	Road proximity
01	0.30	0.05	0.30	0.05	0.30
02	0.10	0.05	0.40	0.05	0.40
03	0.40	0.05	0.10	0.05	0.40
04	0.40	0.05	0.40	0.05	0.10
05	0.25	0.20	0.25	0.05	0.25
06	0.15	0.20	0.30	0.05	0.30
07	0.30	0.20	0.15	0.05	0.30
08	0.30	0.20	0.30	0.05	0.15

Fig. 3. Sensitivity across different two-fold combinations of variable weights (e.g., Biomass against Road Proximity or Slope). The plots of the other two-fold combinations are available in appendices (Figure A4). The black dot is the median sensitivity, the red ribbon the interquartile range, and the grey ribbon the 10th –90th percentile range. The x-axis reports the weight of the second variable in the facet title, the other variable weight complements to 0.9; e.g., in the first top-left facet, a value in the x-axis of 0.3 indicates a weight of road proximity of 0.3 and a weight of biomass of 0.7 (0.9-0.3). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 4. Overview after applying restrictions and weights from the MCA to calculate the original biomass SI at the pixel level of 100 x 100 m (left) and the aggregated outline of potential areas at a coarser resolution of 1 km² (right).

farthest pixel (Eq. (2)), representing the total amount of suitable and close AGB that it could be collected. Lastly, this score was weighted with the DNI value reaching in each city and provided by [22].

Distributions from a single to K optimal SPB locations were evaluated by clustering high suitability pixels into 1 to K groups. For each cluster, the best city location was defined using the simulated annealing (SA) algorithm inserting in Eq. (2) as the cost function. SA was chosen due to its successful implementation in other studies shown in [36], instead of testing alternative metaheuristic optimisation methods. The procedure was implemented in R using the “spsann” package [37], which supports combinatorial multi-objective optimisation problems in large and complex search spaces.

$$V_{k,i} = \left[\sum_{n=1}^N \left(\frac{S_i - \text{Dist}_{n \rightarrow i}}{S_i + \text{Dist}_{n \rightarrow i}} \right) \right] * nDNI_i \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

where $V_{k,i}$ represents the total suitability value for the i th city-hub within cluster k , as determined by the optimisation function. $\text{Dist}_{n \rightarrow i}$ is the distance from pixel n (with suitability S_i) to the i th city-hub,

normalised to [0-1] scale, where 1 corresponds to 100 km. Thus, this term equals 1 at zero distance and approaches 0 when the distance is ≥ 100 km. The term $nDNI$ represents the normalised DNI value at the city-hub location, scaled from 1 to 3 for a DNI range of 1000 to 3000 kWh/m². Cities with DNI values below 1000 kWh/m² were excluded. As shown in Table A2, all cities considered fall within this range.

This formulation produced a final SI value ($V_{k,i}$) for each city i within cluster k , considering all nearby high-AGB pixels and the DNI at the city-hub location. SA performance was tested for convergence and reproducibility by running 12 iterations, which consistently reached a stable minimum of the cost function (Eq. (2)). Sensitivity to initial conditions was tested by executing the model 30 times for each country. All runs yielded identical optimal city-hub configurations, with consistent total suitability values derived from neighbouring AGB pixels. In addition, high DNI at selected hubs ensures adequate renewable energy for carbon-neutral pyrolysis operations, thereby strengthening the technical feasibility of the proposed SPB system.

For each country, high suitability pixels were aggregated into 1 to K

Fig. 5. Optimal number of clusters and hub locations identified using SA. Six hubs in Spain, eight in Italy, and six in Greece are shown. Red pixels indicate high suitability, blue crosses mark alternative large cities, and the black cross identifies the most optimal hub location into the cluster. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

clusters, where N represents the number of large cities that can host a SPB plant (Table A2). Each cluster was wrapped in a convex hull geometry to assess which cities might be considered for potential combinations of an ideal cluster of suitable pixels. To mitigate border effects, i. e., where a city was left out because it was located just outside a cluster, we buffer 50 km of each geometry to include nearby cities. We then ran the optimisation function to determine: (i) the number of clusters that maximises total suitable pixels per city, and (ii) the optimal city within or near (≤ 50 km) each cluster. Initially, all pixels were grouped into a single cluster, and one city was selected to maximise AGB collection within a 100 km radius, considering pine and oak species. However, this configuration likely excluded distant pixels, reducing total AGB collection compared to solutions with multiple cities. As the number of clusters increases, each city may collect fewer suitable pixels individually, thus lowering overall AGB per city, but generally from shorter distances as additional cities capture nearby resources. To assess optimal combinations, we used the cluster and hub definition at the maximum value of total suitability in hubs.

3. Results

3.1. Effective AGB at country and regional scale

Potential and effective AGB were quantified at national (Table 2) and regional levels (Table A3), including area (ha) and AGB (Mg). A significant difference was observed between reductions in area and AGB: the effective area decreased more sharply than AGB after applying environmental and accessibility restrictions. Spain exhibited the largest area loss (79.7%) due to topographical, soil, and forest cover constraints, while AGB decreased less pronounced (32.4%). Despite these

constraints, Italy retained the highest effective AGB (618.5×10^6 Mg), followed by Spain (451.9×10^6 Mg), and Greece (174.9×10^6 Mg).

At regional level, Castile-Leon had the largest potential forest area in Spain (47,210 km²; Table A3), but not the highest effective AGB. Instead, Galicia recorded the highest effective AGB (80.9×10^6 Mg), despite a 39.0% reduction due to restrictions. In Italy, Sardinia had the largest potential forest area (13,547 km²), while Tuscany retained the highest effective AGB (83.9×10^6 Mg), benefiting from relatively low restriction rates (20%). Conversely, mountainous regions such as Aosta Valley (59.2%), Lombardy (51.9%), and Trentino-Alto-Adige (48.9%) experienced substantial area reductions, primarily due to steep terrain. In Greece, Central Greece was the only region exceeding one million hectares of potential forest area (10,025 km²). However, as in other countries, the largest area did not correspond to the highest effective AGB; this was observed in Eastern Macedonia and Thrace.

3.2. Suitability index maps

The results, including maps of effective AGB distribution and suitability levels, are available for download (see Data availability). Selected high-resolution insets are shown in Figure A6 to highlight regions with a high density of pixels exhibiting high SI values, improving visualisation of spatial pattern and key areas. These maps provide practical information for planning the sustainable use and management of AGB. In this study, a proof-of-concept application was conducted using these maps to identify optimal SPB locations by choosing major cities in each country.

Table 2

Statistics of the potential and effective forest areas (ha) after restrictions, and the same for the potential and effective forest AGB (Mg) for Spain, Italy, and Greece, including relative values (%) in both variables.

Country	Potential Area (km ²)	Effective Area (km ²)	Effective Area (%)	Potential Biomass (10 ³ Mg)	Effective Biomass (10 ³ Mg)	Effective Biomass (%)
Spain	269,449	54,640	20.3	668,516	451,937	67.6
Italy	125,973	53,468	42.4	947,201	618,519	65.3
Greece	73,671	20,948	28.4	245,301	174,940	71.3

3.3. Optimal location to store and process forest AGB

To ensure efficient AGB transportation, optimal number and locations of candidate cities for hosting SPB plants were identified for each country using SA. Cities were first spatially clustered, starting from a single cluster and progressively increasing to multiple clusters (Figure A5). Each cluster grouped large cities (Fig. 5), and a suitability score defined in Eq. (2) was assigned to each city. The most suitable city in each cluster was then selected to minimise transport distances and optimise AGB collection. A 100 km radius was applied as the maximum transport distance, with each pixel assigned to its nearest city. Table 3 reports proximal biomass and refines this estimate by excluding Natura 2000 areas, providing an approximation of operable AGB for biorefinery feedstock. The comparison between total and restricted biomass highlights the impact of environmental constraints. Both values are shown, as final use of AGB in protected areas depends on local regulations and ecological assessments.

In Spain, six optimal AGB hubs were identified, each associated to a major city. Logroño (N Spain) had the highest amount of AGB within a 100 km proximity radius, both total and excluding Natura 2000 areas (Fig. 5). It was also among the least affected by conservation constraints and had the highest share of AGB located outside protected areas, highlighting its strong potential as a supply centre. In Italy, eight hubs were identified. Catanzaro (SW Italy) emerged as the leading city in terms of both total proximal AGB and the amount of AGB located in areas outside from Natura 2000 restrictions, indicating a favourable balance between AGB potential and regulatory feasibility. In Greece, six hubs were selected, while Kavala (NE Greece) registered the highest total proximal AGB, the city of Patras had the largest quantity of AGB situated outside Natura 2000 zones. This distinction underscores the importance of considering both AGB potential and regulatory accessibility when selecting sites for bioenergy projects. The full dataset is available through the Data availability section.

3.4. Proximal AGB by tree species targeted group

Proximal AGB outside Natura 2000 areas was classified using the European tree species map [38], which provides distribution for 20 tree species groups at 1 km resolution (Table 4). For this analysis, species were aggregated into three categories: pines, oaks, and others, given that pines and oaks are of primary interest because these are the most

abundant species in Mediterranean ecosystems [39]. All remaining species, including *Castanea* spp., *Fagus* spp. or *Eucalyptus* spp., were grouped as others. In Spain, the most promising hub was Logroño, where pines and oaks accounted for 70% of proximal AGB, increasing to 76% outside Natura 2000 areas. Other notable hubs included Madrid (100% pines and oaks), and Ourense, which showed 86% in both proximal AGB and Natura 2000 free areas between pines and oaks. In Italy, Catanzaro had the highest total AGB but 87% come from species outside the pine and oak categories, whereas Bolzano with 83% pines, better aligned with pyrolysis feedstock requirements. In Greece, Kavala was identified as the optimal hub, with pines and oaks making up 70% of proximal AGB. Patras was also promising, with pines contributing 85% of AGB outside Natura 2000 areas.

4. Discussion

In this study, optimal SPB plant locations were identified based on three main criteria: i) high-value AGB suitability, ii) a road network proximity, and iii) normalised solar irradiation. Road distance and solar irradiation were treated as independent variables and sourced from reliable public datasets. OSM for roads and the World Bank's Global Solar Atlas for long-term, satellite-validated solar data [22]. The AGB suitability map was generated through a multi-stage geospatial approach. First, spatial restrictions excluded unsuitable areas based on topography, soil, and forest cover. Elevation data from ALOS (RMSE 4.4 m; [24]), may have caused minor misclassification in terrain-sensitive areas. Second, a MCA combined vegetation and accessibility variables to prioritise suitable locations, with AGB as the most influential variable, with a continental-scale RMSE of 32.4 Mg/ha [21], potentially propagating uncertainty into final SI values. NPP data from MODIS lacks pixel-level uncertainty estimates, limiting precise error quantification. Road data may introduce minor uncertainties from geolocation errors or incomplete mapping, but these are negligible for large cities with well-structured networks. Overall, uncertainties arise from differences in spatial resolution and data-specific errors, collectively affecting effective AGB estimates and SI calculations.

Suitability assessment is inherently multivariate and can be modelled at varying levels of details. Factors such as collection efficiency, accessibility and transportation losses can impact AGB suitability and can be captured in more detailed models. In this study, we applied simplifications, using road distance and slope as proxies for

Table 3

Optimal locations selected for SPB plants, showing potential and effective AGB (Mg), and proximal AGB within a 100 km radius. Areas outside Natura 2000 restrictions are also identified, indicating the proportion of AGB potentially accessible under current regulations. Values in brackets indicate percentages relative to potential AGB.

Country	City	Mean DNI (kWh/m ² /year)	Potential Biomass (10 ⁶ Mg)	Effective Biomass (10 ⁶ Mg)	Proximal Biomass (10 ⁶ Mg)	Without Natura 2000 (10 ⁶ Mg)
Spain	Algeciras	1812	18.8	11.7 (62.1%)	1.08 (5.8%)	0.01 (0.1%)
Spain	Leon	1959	85.2	41.1 (48.2%)	2.33 (2.7%)	1.66 (1.9%)
Spain	Logroño	1576	99.7	69.6 (69.8%)	24.3 (24.4%)	11.4 (11.5%)
Spain	Madrid	2023	13.9	10.2 (73.8%)	3.07 (22.1%)	0.16 (1.2%)
Spain	Mataro	1699	60.7	37.3 (61.5%)	8.02 (13.2%)	4.29 (7.1%)
Spain	Ourense	1487	131	59.7 (45.6%)	3.52 (2.7%)	3.30 (2.5%)
Italy	Bolzano	1482	283	93.7 (33.1%)	10.3 (3.6%)	7.09 (2.5%)
Italy	Campobasso	1597	50.2	27.6 (54.9%)	2.33 (4.6%)	0.45 (0.9%)
Italy	Catania	1847	22.9	12.5 (54.5%)	3.83 (16.7%)	0.83 (3.6%)
Italy	Catanzaro	1664	68.4	44.0 (64.3%)	13.7 (20.0%)	10.3 (15.0%)
Italy	Genoa	1418	76.2	46.8 (61.4%)	6.40 (8.4%)	5.05 (6.6%)
Italy	Potenza	1588	61.3	37.9 (61.9%)	6.83 (11.2%)	2.41 (3.9%)
Italy	Sassari	1692	12.2	7.38 (60.3%)	0.97 (7.9%)	0.69 (5.6%)
Italy	Siena	1527	11.1	7.47 (67.5%)	1.03 (9.3%)	0.62 (5.6%)
Greece	Ioanina	1614	77.3	39.0 (50.4%)	4.56 (5.9%)	2.39 (3.1%)
Greece	Katerini	1542	29.1	18.3 (62.7%)	2.70 (9.3%)	0.69 (2.4%)
Greece	Kavala	1522	127	38.4 (30.1%)	8.30 (6.5%)	3.44 (2.7%)
Greece	Komatini	1497	103	27.6 (26.7%)	4.82 (4.7%)	2.11 (2.0%)
Greece	Patras	1783	55.9	27.2 (48.6%)	4.58 (8.2%)	3.84 (6.9%)
Greece	Polygyros	1491	22.9	14.9 (65.0%)	2.46 (10.7%)	0.95 (4.1%)

Table 4

Proximal AGB and without Natura 2000 overlapping results showing tree species groups (pines, oaks, and others) in absolute (10^3 Mg) and relative (%) values in brackets for optimal hubs in Spain, Italy, and Greece; the city with the highest unrestricted biomass is in bold.

Country	City	Proximal Biomass			Without Natura 2000		
		Pines	Oaks	Others	Pines	Oaks	Others
Spain	Algeciras	561.6 (52)	518.4 (48)	0	7.6 (72)	2.9 (28)	0
Spain	Leon	1980.5 (85)	93.2 (4)	256.3 (11)	1427.6 (86)	83.0 (5)	149.4 (9)
Spain	Logroño	10,206.0 (42)	6804.0 (28)	7290.0 (30)	5700.0 (50)	2964.0 (26)	2736.0 (24)
Spain	Madrid	2732.3 (89)	337.7 (11)	0	97.2 (60)	64.8 (40)	0
Spain	Mataro	1924.8 (24)	5694.2 (71)	401.0 (5)	1458.6 (34)	2659.8 (62)	171.6 (4)
Spain	Ourense	2921.6 (83)	105.6 (3)	492.8 (14)	2739.0 (83)	99.0 (3)	462.0 (14)
Italy	Bolzano	8549.0 (83)	0	1751.0 (17)	6026.5 (85)	70.9 (1)	992.6 (14)
Italy	Campobasso	0	1234.9 (53)	1095.1 (47)	0	300.1 (67)	147.8 (33)
Italy	Catania	421.3 (11)	3255.5 (85)	153.2 (4)	265.2 (32)	472.5 (57)	91.1 (11)
Italy	Catanzaro	1781.0 (13)	0	11,919.0 (87)	927.0 (9)	0	9373.0 (91)
Italy	Genoa	0	960.0 (15)	5440.0 (85)	50.5 (1)	656.5 (13)	4343.0 (86)
Italy	Potenza	0	5327.4 (78)	1502.6 (22)	0	2241.3 (93)	168.7 (7)
Italy	Sassari	9.6 (1)	959.3 (99)	0	0	689.0 (100)	0
Italy	Siena	1030.0 (10)	5150.0 (50)	4120.0 (40)	309.5 (6)	3218.8 (52)	2661.7 (42)
Greece	Ioanina	2188.8 (48)	1596.0 (35)	775.2 (17)	1099.4 (46)	812.6 (34)	478.0 (20)
Greece	Katerini	270.0 (10)	216.0 (8)	2214.0 (82)	55.2 (8)	82.9 (12)	552.8 (80)
Greece	Kavala	2490.0 (30)	3320.0 (40)	2490.0 (30)	550.4 (16)	1720.0 (50)	1169.6 (34)
Greece	Komatini	1590.6 (33)	2554.6 (53)	674.8 (14)	379.8 (18)	1392.6 (66)	337.6 (16)
Greece	Patras	3893.0 (85)	137.4 (3)	549.6 (12)	3264.0 (85)	38.4 (1)	537.6 (14)
Greece	Polygyros	369.0 (15)	369.0 (15)	1722.0 (70)	37.9 (4)	294.1 (31)	616.8 (65)

these factors. While this may be a limitation, assuming these variables adequately represent overall AGB accessibility and collection efficiency, it remains the most feasible approach for analyses at a national-scale.

4.1. Threshold to determine effective AGB and MCA weights

Restrictions to identify effective AGB areas began with mechanisation concerns, as logging on steep terrain is technically challenging, hazardous and costly [40]. A uniform slope threshold of 50% was applied across the three countries, although [25] indicates that ground-based forest machinery operates most efficiently on slopes up to 30%. A stricter 30% threshold would have excluded many areas with considerable AGB potential and reduced eligible SI pixels. Moreover, the proportion of useable SI pixels varies with the specific topography of each country and region, reflecting the heterogeneity of Mediterranean sub-regions in terms of terrain, climate, and forest composition. The 50% threshold was therefore adopted to be more inclusive, allowing additional forested areas to be considered through adapted harvesting options and machinery [26]. Alternative thresholds could be defined to reflect country or region-specific conditions, as the results are sensitive to the slope parameter. In addition to slope, restrictions based on soil type and forest cover were applied, primarily to ensure technical feasibility and support conservation objectives. These filters excluded areas where harvesting might be environmentally undesirable or operationally unfeasible. Furthermore, thresholds were applied to five variables used in the MCA to refine the suitability assessment. During the normalisation, each dataset's distribution was carefully analysed to detect and manage outliers. This step was critical to avoid distortion of the resulting suitability scores, as uncorrected outliers could produce skewed values, underestimating areas with genuine AGB potential.

4.2. SI maps integrated with DNI and road network

Eight MCA scenarios were developed, with consistent results across them. Consequently, the choice of scenario did not significantly affect the final outcomes. Scenario 2 was selected because it yielded the largest suitable area (Figure A5), although differences among scenarios were minimal. The selected suitability map was then combined with DNI and the road network. DNI values were normalised using a threshold of 1000 kWh/m²/year, excluding areas with lower values. According to [41], under European climatic conditions, annual DNI values between

1400 and 1800 kWh/m²/year are considered adequate for solar-biomass hybrid power plants. These thresholds align with the mean DNI levels observed in the selected cities, where minimum values were Ourense (1, 487), Genoa (1,418), and Polygyros (1,491). None of the selected SPB locations had DNI values below 1400 kWh/m²/year (Table 3). Road data were sourced from OSM, which generally provides higher road density compared to datasets used in previous studies. However, forest road data can be highly variable and often incomplete, particularly in forested environments. As a result, areas with high AGB potential may appear unsuitable if routes are not fully mapped. An underrepresentation of roads could exclude areas that are actually accessible, potentially increasing transportation costs for supplying AGB to SPB plants. Efficient AGB extraction and transport depend heavily on road accessibility, as harvesting and forwarding machinery require proper access to operate efficiently. A well-mapped forest road system reduces transportation costs and maximises profitability for AGB products. High-resolution forest road maps from LiDAR data, which is available in some countries; for example, Spain's National Aerial Orthophotography Plan provides nationwide LiDAR coverage. Such datasets could be used to produce accurate road and forest trails maps in areas with limited accessibility. However, this approach is restricted to countries where such information is available.

4.3. Identification of hubs and tree species classification

The optimal number of clusters was determined using spatial and statistical analyses (Fig. 5). The figure represents both the spatial distribution of clusters across the three countries (top), and the ideal number of clusters derived from aggregated SI values (bottom). Within each cluster, the most suitable hub was selected to ensure proportional representation across countries. In total, six clusters were identified in Spain, eight in Italy, and six in Greece. For each hub, the amount of AGB within a 100 km radius, which was defined as proximal AGB, was calculated from the city centre. Since the clusters were determined at national level, the resulting proximal AGB values were heterogeneous (Table 3). Some clusters, such as Algeciras in Spain, that even before the Natura 2000 restrictions, have demonstrated low values, which decreased from 5.8% to 0.1%. Nevertheless, certain silvicultural treatments may still be allowed under specific regulations, as not all Natura 2000 sites enforce the same level of protection, allowing for some AGB extraction in restricted areas.

Initially, proximal AGB included all tree species, but this study focused on pine and oak species due to their abundance in Mediterranean ecosystems and suitability for pyrolysis feedstock. The European tree species distribution map [38] was employed. While valuable at a continental scale, this dataset is relatively coarse (1 km resolution) and includes tree species beyond the target groups. Therefore, all species not classified as pines or oaks were grouped as other species. The proportion of biomass attributed to these three groups is critical, especially when the pyrolysis process requires feedstocks with specific lignocellulosic properties. However, the results derived from the [38] map should be interpreted with caution due to its limited spatial accuracy and inherent uncertainties in tree species classification. At a 1 km resolution, individual pixels may contain multiple species, potentially biasing the estimated contribution of each tree-species group to proximal AGB. Recent advances in remote sensing and artificial intelligence have shown promising results for tree species identification. For instance [42], report high classification accuracies using novel sensors and algorithms. Nevertheless, these approaches have so far been applied only at local or regional scales, and harmonised continental-scale datasets remain scarce. Therefore, improving future AGB assessment for SPB plants will require the development and adoption of standardized tree species classification methodologies across national boundaries. Implementing high-resolution sensors and AI-driven models at the country or continental level would significantly enhance accuracy, reduce uncertainties in AGB estimates and support better-informed decision-making for bioenergy planning.

6. Code availability

Code is available upon reasonable request.

7. Conclusions

In this study, we developed a 1 km-resolution geospatial dataset of SI maps to identify optimal locations for SPB plants utilising AGB for solar-pyrolysis. The analysis integrates spatial factors, including accessibility and vegetational constraints related to topography, soil characteristics, and protected areas, as well as a minimum forest cover threshold required to qualify as effective AGB. Additional variables, such as growth productivity, forest cover, slope, and road proximity, were incorporated into a MCA framework to compute an aggregated suitability score. Optimisation was conducted using SA, which efficiently explores the best distribution of suitable AGB into spatial clusters. A tailored cost-function balanced multiple objectives, including minimising transport distance, maximising DNI, and ensuring sufficient AGB availability, while respecting environmental and technical constraints to select the most suitable city within each cluster for allocating a SPB plant. Our proof-of-concept application demonstrates the value of this approach by identifying optimal biomass pyrolysis sites across three EU Mediterranean countries. Overall, the dataset and methodology provide a reproducible and scalable decision-support tool for planners, policy-makers, and researchers seeking to optimise biorefinery siting in a spatially explicit and sustainable manner. Future research should

prioritise detailed local-scale assessment of the high-potential clusters identified here. Such analysis should validate AGB resource availability using local forest inventories, refine transport and infrastructure assumptions, and conduct comprehensive site-specific evaluation of environmental constraints. In particular, further work should quantify land acquisition costs, forest AGB feedstock costs, and transport costs, while simultaneously assessing the environmental implications of AGB extraction at selected sites.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Erico Kutchartt: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Francesco Pirotti:** Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **José Salgado-Rojas:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Álvaro Cortés-Molino:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Núria Aquilué:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Neus Puy:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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Appendices.

Fig. A1. Histogram distribution of the five variables used in the MCA with scaling functions in Spain to transform the absolute values from [0-1], using percentiles of 1, 2, and 5% to define the minimum and maximum values.

Fig. A2. Histogram distribution of the five variables used in the MCA with scaling functions in Italy to transform the absolute values from [0-1], using percentiles of 1, 2, and 5% to define the minimum and maximum values.

Fig. A3. Histogram distribution of the five variables used in the MCA with scaling functions in Greece to transform the absolute values from [0-1], using percentiles of 1, 2, and 5% to define the minimum and maximum values.

Fig. A4. Sensitivity analysis of pairwise variable combinations was performed for Spain, Italy, and Greece. Each variable was paired with another to examine the extent to which variations in one variable influenced the sensitivity value response (y-axis) changing their relative weights (x-axis). The ratio of paired variable weights total 0.9, because the rest is evenly distributed as fixed weights on the remaining variables. Thus, the weight of the first variable drives the rest, e.g., if it is 0.5, the second variable will be 0.9-0.5. The black point, the red and grey ribbon are respectively the median, the interquartile range and the 10th –90th percentile range of sensitivity values.

Fig. A4. (continued).

Fig. A5. Integrating SI map results with DNI values to identify optimal locations for AGB storage in each country, ensuring a maximum distance of 100 km. The eight scenarios correspond to those in Table 1, sorted by AGB availability, NPP, forest cover, slope, and road proximity.

Fig. A6. SI maps displaying values ranging from [0-1] for Spain, Italy, and Greece (left column), alongside zoomed-in views highlighting regions with a high concentration of pixels exhibiting high SI values (right column).

Table A1

Minimum and maximum values are based on the 1st percentile and 99th percentile, serving as the lower and upper threshold criteria. Additional graphical details are provided in Figures A1, A2, and A3.

Country	AGB availability (Mg/ha)	Net primary productivity (kgC/ha/year)	Forest cover (%)	Slope (%)	Road proximity log(m)
Spain	5.30-215.50	3962-12789	50.43-97.47	3.74-49.39	1.00-3.22
Italy	8.69-296.55	4351-12777	50.97-98.48	6.14-49.57	1.00-3.07
Greece	8.02-242.99	3524-13296	50.66-99.27	8.52-49.54	1.00-3.26

Table A2

For each country, the number of main cities considered (N) and descriptive statistics of the distribution of DNI values for the cities. More details about DNI values (kWh/m²) at the region level are provided in Table A4.

Country	N	Min.	1st Qu.	Median	Mean	3rd Qu.	Max.
Greece	30	1419	1584	1714	1686	1792	1944
Italy	56	1342	1466	1567	1561	1650	1842
Spain	49	1009	1576	1855	1763	2032	2196

Table A3

Statistics of the potential and effective forest areas (ha) after restrictions, and the same for the potential and effective AGB (Mg) for all the regions of Spain, Italy, and Greece according to the NUTS levels, including relative values (%) in both attributes.

Country	Regions	Potential Area (ha)	Effective Area (ha)	Effective Area (%)	Potential Biomass (Mg)	Effective Biomass (Mg)	Effective Biomass (%)
Spain	Galicia	1,968,908	660,465	33.5	132,714,646	80,998,036	61.0
Spain	Principality of Asturias	764,428	296,250	38.8	58,748,764	36,483,808	62.1
Spain	Cantabria	353,610	149,126	42.2	19,055,970	13,285,052	69.7
Spain	Basque Country	471,593	271,450	57.6	40,892,281	30,817,164	75.4
Spain	Navarra	574,503	291,255	50.7	45,758,068	38,497,929	84.1
Spain	La Rioja	304,784	109,299	35.9	11,236,376	9,003,079	80.1
Spain	Aragon	2,505,203	494,503	19.7	57,628,442	38,798,923	67.3
Spain	Madrid	404,959	60,180	14.9	4,204,337	3,421,208	81.4
Spain	Castile-Leon	4,720,998	1,008,675	21.4	94,865,401	69,072,521	72.8
Spain	Castile-La Mancha	3,621,737	454,061	12.5	30,781,253	19,063,819	61.9
Spain	Extremadura	2,605,081	232,145	8.9	15,187,197	9,651,745	63.6
Spain	Catalonia	1,920,300	729,240	38.0	96,590,344	68,549,093	71.0
Spain	Valencian Community	1,293,554	148,581	11.5	10,749,826	5,726,508	53.3
Spain	Balearic Islands	202,361	46,768	23.1	3,632,070	2,331,965	64.2
Spain	Andalusia	4,230,803	462,893	10.9	41,173,159	23,798,669	57.8
Spain	Murcia	457,051	21,514	4.7	1,726,936	730,694	42.3
Italy	Piemont	1,283,743	461,189	35.9	95,346,722	53,470,719	56.1
Italy	Aosta Valley	294,286	34,737	11.8	14,438,792	5,896,233	40.8
Italy	Liguria	421,096	257,377	61.1	35,526,434	27,001,315	76.0
Italy	Lombardy	911,496	285,901	31.4	99,343,316	47,780,252	48.1
Italy	Abruzzo	560,463	227,955	40.7	32,938,804	24,897,238	75.6
Italy	Molise	161,549	91,271	56.5	7,332,650	6,181,510	84.3
Italy	Campania	505,085	272,018	53.9	31,936,134	23,731,272	74.3
Italy	Apulia	244,370	73,118	29.9	3,964,112	3,166,458	79.9
Italy	Basilicata	409,790	217,041	53.0	23,089,410	19,774,577	85.6
Italy	Calabria	720,912	407,182	56.5	79,266,687	62,888,700	79.3
Italy	Sicily	667,125	172,800	25.9	19,428,141	14,794,531	76.2
Italy	Sardinia	1,354,681	437,962	32.3	22,826,264	16,454,668	72.1
Italy	Trentino Alto-Adige	617,558	160,447	26.0	62,549,031	31,985,300	51.1
Italy	Bolzano	520,284	180,113	34.6	68,227,141	36,934,092	54.1
Italy	Veneto	531,151	209,308	39.4	69,822,082	41,016,480	58.7
Italy	Friuli-Venezia Giulia	404,923	156,474	38.6	60,909,708	32,141,742	52.8
Italy	Emilia-Romagna	585,233	367,780	62.8	43,398,153	35,552,383	81.9
Italy	Tuscany	1,125,039	743,630	66.1	104,968,463	83,979,448	80.0
Italy	Umbria	370,135	175,636	47.5	17,130,174	11,974,653	69.9
Italy	Marche	293,739	112,840	38.4	16,094,691	10,091,298	62.7
Italy	Lazio	614,581	301,950	49.1	38,660,977	28,803,809	74.5
Greece	Attica	191,187	24,086	12.6	2,522,548	1,125,455	44.6
Greece	North Aegean	218,283	38,796	17.8	2,317,920	1,540,722	66.5
Greece	South Aegean	344,674	16,888	4.9	1,306,351	559,699	42.8
Greece	Crete	449,206	16,815	3.7	2,282,158	727,325	31.9
Greece	Eastern Macedonia and Thrace	797,435	351,635	44.1	53,530,004	42,130,028	78.7
Greece	Central Macedonia	788,457	322,809	40.9	28,600,897	22,314,242	78.0
Greece	Western Macedonia	558,983	163,407	29.2	16,526,321	12,969,363	78.5
Greece	Epirus	665,896	248,640	37.3	32,456,616	23,888,256	73.6
Greece	Thessaly	745,649	243,431	32.6	28,010,035	20,818,946	74.3
Greece	Ionian Islands	100,275	16,009	16.0	1,532,076	752,461	49.1
Greece	Western Greece	596,572	158,848	26.6	17,921,530	11,083,044	61.8
Greece	Central Greece	1,002,371	296,592	29.6	38,922,774	25,072,163	64.4
Greece	Peloponnese	908,048	196,836	21.7	19,371,333	11,957,632	61.7

Table A4
Statistics of the Direct Normal Irradiation (DNI; kWh/m²) values for the regions in Spain, Italy, and Greece.

Country	Regions	DNI (Max)	DNI (Min)	DNI (Mean ± SD)
Spain	Galicia	1891	584	1393 ± 190
Spain	Principality of Asturias	1683	344	1111 ± 125
Spain	Cantabria	1715	372	1176 ± 166
Spain	Basque Country	1599	460	1178 ± 150
Spain	Navarra	1872	635	1498 ± 239
Spain	La Rioja	1807	902	1552 ± 113
Spain	Aragon	2091	442	1878 ± 128
Spain	Madrid	2117	1380	2007 ± 91
Spain	Castile-Leon	2150	460	1864 ± 180
Spain	Castile-La Mancha	2190	945	2042 ± 78
Spain	Extremadura	2183	1142	2076 ± 58
Spain	Catalonia	2095	449	1747 ± 150
Spain	Valencian Community	2099	821	1874 ± 95
Spain	Balearic Islands	1836	456	1683 ± 89
Spain	Andalusia	2431	945	2074 ± 93
Spain	Murcia	2241	1113	1987 ± 85
Italy	Piemont	1913	306	1405 ± 176
Italy	Aosta Valley	1905	478	1406 ± 224
Italy	Liguria	1723	555	1343 ± 113
Italy	Lombardy	1759	156	1373 ± 153
Italy	Abruzzo	1778	297	1516 ± 127
Italy	Molise	1675	891	1565 ± 71
Italy	Campania	1737	741	1537 ± 101
Italy	Apulia	1788	1190	1667 ± 52
Italy	Basilicata	1705	80	1587 ± 67
Italy	Calabria	1854	664	1594 ± 115
Italy	Sicily	1956	496	1766 ± 111
Italy	Sardinia	1840	770	1697 ± 74
Italy	Trentino Alto-Adige	1752	227	1260 ± 213
Italy	Bolzano	1734	223	1246 ± 210
Italy	Veneto	1540	6	1316 ± 155
Italy	Friuli-Venezia Giulia	1471	231	1218 ± 192
Italy	Emilia-Romagna	1591	631	1448 ± 67
Italy	Tuscany	1752	260	1503 ± 118
Italy	Umbria	1741	599	1531 ± 90
Italy	Marche	1642	464	1456 ± 104
Italy	Lazio	1774	788	1617 ± 101
Greece	Attica	1898	1234	1745 ± 66
Greece	North Aegean	1978	1033	1785 ± 87
Greece	South Aegean	2048	1058	1867 ± 107
Greece	Crete	2190	803	1834 ± 114
Greece	Eastern Macedonia and Thrace	1661	668	1455 ± 83
Greece	Central Macedonia	1683	460	1514 ± 81
Greece	Western Macedonia	1701	956	1547 ± 81
Greece	Epirus	1814	562	1576 ± 125
Greece	Thessaly	1715	356	1546 ± 103
Greece	Ionioan Islands	1818	1055	1672 ± 79
Greece	Western Greece	1883	668	1689 ± 122
Greece	Central Greece	1832	624	1582 ± 121
Greece	Peloponnese	1927	843	1702 ± 102

Data availability

The dataset is openly available on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14834389>. It includes all MCA variables in both original values and normalised form [0,1], structured in a stack format. The dataset also provides SI maps for all eight scenarios across the three countries, supporting comparative evaluation and reproducibility.

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